

STRENGTHENING THE MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL BASE OF AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the strengthening of the material and technical base of agriculture, the economic aspect of agricultural development.*

Key words: *Agriculture, Collective farms, Administrative management, industrialization-agriculture.*

УКРЕПЛЕНИЕ МАТЕРИАЛЬНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ БАЗЫ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА

Аннотация. *В данной статье основное внимание уделяется укреплению материально-технической базы сельского хозяйства, экономическому аспекту развития сельского хозяйства.*

Ключевые слова: *Сельское хозяйство, Колхозы, Административное управление, индустриализация-сельское хозяйство.*

In the late 1950s, five-year planning was switched to seven-year planning (1959-1965). Since that time, the process of squeezing economic incentives for agricultural development by administrative force began. Initially, the state allocated huge funds for strengthening the material and technical base of agriculture. It should be recognized that the funds spent on agriculture in Karakalpakstan helped to provide water for the republic's cotton farming and develop reserve lands for rice cultivation.

However, in allocating funds for agriculture, especially in the 1960s, factors such as the development of state and collective farms, reorganization of MTS, increase in the prices of agricultural machinery, its parts, feed products and mineral fertilizers were not taken into account. For example, in 1959 MTSs were changed to repair tractor stations (TTS). The equipment was sold by the collective farm. But the decision in this regard was unsuccessful, moreover, in many cases it damaged the economy of collective farms. Because it was not possible to pay the price of TTS equipment in installments or buy it for the nation.

As of July 1, 1958, their prices were increased by 1.5-2 times on average. Equipment had to be purchased at fairly high prices. In collective farms, there were cases of insufficient funds, exceeding the costs of using equipment. After the transformation of MTSs, their costs for providing equipment, using and training specialists in this field have increased. All this had a negative impact on the production of state and collective farms. Their financial situation worsened. Moreover, these factors, which require the most attention, have seriously changed the existing conditions in state and collective farms. The production costs of these farms have increased.

In 1961, a number of specific measures were implemented to improve the economic and financial situation of state and collective farms. Agricultural machinery and their spare parts, fuel and vehicles were reduced by an average of 40 percent for collective farms. In March 1962, the purchase prices of milk and dairy products, cattle and poultry were increased by an average of 35%. The government authorized the Councils of Ministers of the Union Republics to delay payments for the purchase of MTS equipment by collective farms.

The measures taken have significantly improved the condition of farms and strengthened their material and technical base. But even so, these measures could not be considered sufficient to fulfill the tasks set in the program of production of state and collective farms. For example, during the reorganization of the farm management apparatus, the machine tractor stations (MTS) were abolished, all the equipment in them had to be purchased by collective farms. According to those in the government, this would increase the efficiency of the use of machinery and the quality of tillage. However, the activities carried out in accordance with the tasks specified in the decision caused a lot of losses - collective farms were forced to buy equipment at high prices within a year, and in the case of increased purchase prices, it was not possible for collective farms to find funds for the immediate purchase of MTS equipment.

The termination of MTSs led to the destruction and liquidation of many collective farms. Another negative consequence was the loss of cleaners and repairmen who were previously under the care of MTS. Officially, they were supposed to go to collective farms, but this required them to go to a working day, which was much lower than the wages they received before, so some of them went to urban and district centers. The attitude towards the equipment has also changed, because the collective farms, as a rule, did not have parks to store the equipment in the winter, and the level of technical culture of the members of the collective farms was still very low. In addition, the equipment route from fields to fields is long, fuel costs have increased, and due to poor roads, there have been frequent breakdowns.

In order to industrialize agriculture, collective farms were enlarged (as a result, their number was halved), and collective farms were massively transformed into state farms. In the same year, a certain part of the land was cut off from the members of the collective farms, and the cattle were violently seized, and the struggle with the transition to private farms ("farm capitalism") began. As a result, private households fell into a dire situation and food problems intensified.

In November 1961, at the meeting of republican growers held in Tashkent city, the issues of cotton crop productivity were discussed. After the meeting, all state and community farms were given a "secret instruction" to develop measures to achieve a yield of 25 quintals per hectare by each farm from next year. This process had to be initiated through the industrialization of agriculture. . The transformation of MTS in the conditions of Karakalpakstan was completed by the beginning of 1959. Local authorities have demonstrated the ability to carry out government decisions without paying attention to anything. The forced sale of MTS equipment by them led to a huge debt of collective farms. Most of them have reduced their weekday fees. The expectations of collective farms that MTSs would be changed due to better use of technology turned out to be in vain. The purchase of equipment owned by MTS by the collective farms has led to the destruction of a certain part of the collective farms or their expansion, which has not benefited the collective farms, and has caused the disappearance of small villages.

At the March Plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU (1965), the tasks related to the strict strengthening of the technical base of state and collective farms were put forward. In 1965, the total number of agricultural tractors (in physical units) was 78 million. 1.6 million horsepower. established in 1980. — a total of 191 mln. 2.6 million horsepower. organized. During these years, self-propelled combine harvesters increased by 1.4 times, trucks by 1.7 times. Electricity supply to agriculture has also increased dramatically. This made it possible to increase

the total irrigated land area of Karakalpakstan to 230,000 hectares by the beginning of the 1970s. Until now, there were 73 state farms and 42 collective farms in Karakalpakstan. The share of the cotton industry was 2/3 of the irrigated area. All 42 collective farms, 38 out of 73 state farms are specialized in cotton cultivation. Although cotton was cultivated in our region even before the establishment of Soviet power, it did not play an important role in the agricultural economy during this period. For example, if in 1913 the share of cotton in the total cultivated area was only a little more than 10% or 12 thousand hectares, by the 1970s about 70% of the total cultivated area or about 120 thousand hectares were allocated to cotton. True, by this time the productivity of the cotton crop had increased: if in 1963 it was 15.8 centners per hectare, in 1970 the productivity increased to 27.7 centners, by 1975 it was 31 centners per hectare. These figures were associated with the dramatic expansion of land reclamation, as well as the widespread use of pesticides and chemicals. Although the harm of excessive chemicalization of agriculture is obvious, it remained one of the components of agricultural policy until the early 1990s.

During 1971-1972, 5,066 hectares of new land were acquired by Karakalpakstan state farms, improvement of land reclamation was carried out on 26,505 hectares, canals and sewers were restored on 11,260 hectares. For example, in 1971-1972, 44,100 tons of cotton, 3,700 tons of grain and 14,400 tons of vegetables were grown by Karakalpakstan collective farms in comparison to the first two years of the eighth five-year plan. In 1973, 330,000 tons of raw cotton were delivered, which was 108 percent of the national economy plan.

According to the task of the center, in 1973, Karakalpakstan party and state bodies set the task of increasing cotton raw materials to at least 450-500 thousand tons by the end of the decade, increasing other crops of plant science and livestock products. During 1974-1980, at least 150,000 hectares of new land, including ancient irrigated cotton fields in Tortkol, Beruni districts, 20,000 hectares in the Ellikkala massif and 40,000 hectares in Jonboskala, 40,000 hectares for rice in the northern regions, potatoes, vegetables, and 10,000 hectares of arable land were developed for fodder crops and planned to be used in agriculture. A number of activities related to water management, for example, accelerating the construction of the Kyzylkum collector, starting the construction of the Beruni collector, solving the issue of drainage of groundwater (removal of soil deposits) through the territory of Turkmenistan in the Amudarya district and Chigatabin collector, as well as collectors in Leninabad, Shumanay and Khojaly districts. It is planned to complete the construction and build new stations. Also, by the end of the five-year period, construction of 9,400 hydrotechnical structures, including 1,300 structures in the domestic household collector-drainage and irrigation network, taking into account the needs of irrigation of the lands to be developed in the Ellikkala region, all existing collectors and drains belonging to domestic households, the Cotton-arna canal will be re-constructed. restoration and solving other issues was envisaged.

It was during this period that the water management of Karakalpakstan became a complex network system. The works carried out on irrigation of the lands caused certain changes in the development of the republic's agriculture. Cultivated areas exceeded 67 thousand hectares, for the first time an engineered rice system was created on 50 thousand hectares of land. The production of cotton raw materials has increased significantly. In 1974, 196,000 tons of raw cotton or 53% of the total harvest was harvested by machines in Karakalpakstan. At the same time, great importance

was attached to the development of the largest industrial sector in our republic - the cotton ginning industry. In the 1970s, 10 cotton factories, 32 processing stations, several dozen drying and cleaning shops equipped with high-efficiency equipment were built in Karakalpakstan. In the second half of the 1970s, the process of farm specialization was continued: in the middle of 1970, 82 out of 119 state and collective farms were specialized in cotton production, 7 - rice, 7 - vegetables, potatoes, fruits and grapes. As a result of concentration of production in one place, 8 state sheep breeding farms, 14 meat breeding cattle farms and 1 poultry farming state farms intended for fattening large horned cattle were established.

However, cotton cultivation hindered the process of diversification of the agricultural and industrial structure (that is, the process of expanding production activities due to the increase in product types). The experience of those years showed that the fertile republic, which is rich in bioclimatic benefits, has turned into a narrow area of the cotton-growing specialty at the level of the All-Union. In 1970, cotton cultivated areas in Uzbekistan accounted for 50% of all cultivated areas, and only 3.6% of the land area was allocated for spring wheat. The food arable land was rapidly reduced, and the size of private households of the villagers was limited. In Karakalpakstan, the development of new land for the rice complex was continued. In 1974, collective farms of Karakalpakstan sold 120,000 tons of raw rice to the state, or seven times more than in 1966. In 1965, the area planted with rice was 13,600 hectares, and by 1974, this indicator was 35,600 hectares.

In general, Karakalpakstan's monoculture agricultural sector has turned the republic from an agricultural producer to a consumer. Not only grain products, but also some types of potatoes, vegetables and fruits began to be imported to the republic. Uncontrolled use of Amudarya and Syrdarya waters led to global changes in water flows: if in 1961-1970 the average annual flow of water entering the Aral Sea was 42.9 km³, in the early 1980s it was 4.2 km³ . reduced to the amount of . This was one of the main reasons for the tragedy of the Aral Sea. Water, considered invaluable in desert, semi-desert and arid natural environments, has become an almost free resource in an economy that is not suitable for a market economy, focused only on increasing the quantity, not the quality. Thousands of cubic meters of water from this resource were pumped through multiple irrigation systems to irrigate cotton and rice fields, which caused the evaporated water to cover the surface layer with salt.

In Karakalpakstan, the chemicalization of the agricultural network was also carried out on a large scale. In 1960, 172,000 tons of mineral fertilizers were given to the state and collective farms of Karakalpakstan, and in 1970, more than 347,000 tons. Chemical processes led to an increase in oncological and acute respiratory diseases in Karakalpakstan, and people became dependent on the extensive economy of the Soviet state.

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